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Abstract: This article contains a lot of information about the life and work of our great grandfather Abul Abbas Ahmad ibn Muhammad ibn Kasir al-Farghani. In particular, information about where he was born and created, and his great wisdom was given and studied.

Key words: Astronomy, Alfraganus, mathematics, geography, technology, astronomy, astronomy.

Ahmad al-Farghani (full name Abul Abbas Ahmed ibn Muhammad ibn Kasir al-Farghani) (about 797, Ferghana - 865, Egypt) - worked in astronomy, mathematics, geography and other scientific fields. Uzbek encyclopedist. Al-Farghani is known in the East, Alfraganus in Europe. Little, if any, information about his life and scientific activity has come down. Ahmad al-Farghani's life, scientific research and maturity The Abbasid dynasty ruled, the Arab caliphate became one of the largest kingdoms in the world, and many thinkers from Mowarounnahr, Khorezm and Khorasan began to have an important place in its socio-political and cultural life. passed in the historical period. Al-Farghani lived during the reigns of Caliph Harun al-Rashid (786–809), the successors of al-Ma'mun (813–833), Mu'tasim (833–842), and Mutawakkil (846–861), and first Marw, then In the cities of Baghdad, Damascus and Cairo, he was engaged in the

sciences of *ilm* hayat (astronomy, astronomy), *riziyat* (mathematics) and geography (geography) and wrote a number of scientific and practical works. Ahmad al-Farghani first came to Marv from Ferghana (around 811).

In the early Middle Ages, Marv was one of the major cultural and scientific-educational centers of Central Asia. Many scholars, scholars and thinkers from Movarounnahr, Khorezm, and Khorasan gathered in this place and held conferences to discuss their cultural life. are important. Even in 651, Yazdigard III ibn Shahriyar (632-651), the last Sassanid king, fled from Arab persecution and brought the books from the capital's library with him to Marv. Even after the Caliphate, Marv did not lose its ancient status and became not only a scientific and cultural center, but also a political center of the conquered eastern regions. After Harun al-Rashid's death (809), Muhammad al-Amin (809-813) ascended the caliphate throne. His struggle for the throne with his brother Abd Allah (809-813) (Harun al-Rashid sent his son Abd Allah to Marw as the viceroy of Mowarunnahr and Khurasan in 806) ended with Abd Allah's victory. Muhammad al-Amin will be executed. In the same year (813), he ascended the throne under the name Abdullah al-Mamun. However, he did not go to Baghdad, the capital of the caliphate, but lived in Marv until 819. He gathers scholars and virtues around him. In 819, al-Ma'mun moved from Mara to Baghdad with all his courtiers and scholars. Among them was al-Farghani. During this period, the caliphate had two observatories and a rich library built by the order of Harun al-Rashid. According to Abu Rayhan Beruni, one of the observatories was located in al-Shammosiya neighborhood of Baghdad, and the other one was located on a mountain called Kasiyun near Damascus. In the observatories, scientists of the scientific center "Bait ul-Hikmat" ("House of the Wise"), founded by Harun al-Rashid, conducted scientific research. Among them was al-Farghani. Al-Farghani first worked at the observatory in Baghdad, and then, on the instructions of al-Mamun, he led the work of determining the movement and position of celestial bodies and creating a

new "Zij" at the observatory in Damascus. Al-Farghani took an active part in important research conducted by Greek astronomers, including reviewing the information given in Ptolemy's Table of Stars and re-determining the geographical coordinates of all the main places of that time. In this regard, Al-Farghani has a great service in carrying out special scientific works such as defining the terms related to astronomy, mathematics and geography in the Arabic language. In addition to these, he also made an important contribution to the invention of some astronomical instruments, the definition and regulation of the basic knowledge of astronomy in Arabic. In 832-833, al-Farghani took part in measuring the length of one degree of the earth's meridian between Tadmur and al-Raqqa in the Sinjar plain in the north of Syria (Syria). The latest information about Al-Farghani's life and scientific and practical activities dates back to 861. In the same year, the Abbasid caliph Abul Fazl Ja'far al-Mutawakkil (reigned 847-861) came to Fustat, Egypt, near Cairo, to build a facility that would measure the water level of the Nile. This magnificent scientific-technical and architectural device has been preserved until now in the Sayolat ul Rod region of the Nile. Although there is very little information about Al-Farghani, his name was famous in the Eastern scientific world in the Middle Ages.

Ibn Annadim 10th century, Ibn al-Kifti 12th-13th centuries, Abul Faraj Bar Ebrey (13th century) and Haji Khalifa 17th century recorded his name in their works. On December 5, 1997, the members of the expedition named after Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, who traveled through Muslim countries, visited MAR and studied the life of Al-Farghani. As a result, he died in the city of Fustat, Egypt, located a little further from the eastern part of Mount Munattam. They found out that he was buried in the cemetery of Imam ash-Shofe. Over time, his grave disappeared. The soil brought from there was placed in a symbolic grave built in 1998 in the city of Kuva, Fergana Valley. It is recorded in the written sources that Al-Farghani wrote several scientific and practical works in the field

of astronomy, mathematics and geography in the early Middle Ages. His main astronomical work is "Kitab al-harakot as-samovia wa javami' ilm an-nujum" ("The Book of Celestial Movements and General Science of Astrology"). This work, also known as the Book of the Principles of Astronomy, was translated into Latin in Europe between 1145 and 1175. After that, Al-Farghani's name was latinized and became famous in the West in the form of "Alfraganus". His work "The Book of Fundamentals of Astronomy" was used as the main textbook on astronomy in European universities for several centuries, because it contained the most important and necessary knowledge about astronomy of its time. Its section on geography, the most scientific heritage of the Earth's countries and cities, is dedicated to elementary and essential knowledge, and is called "On the Names of Certain Countries and Cities on Earth and the Phenomena in Each Climate." In the work, the main content, tasks and parts of the sciences of disaster and geography are explained in a simple way on the basis of understandable arguments. In particular, valuable comments are made about the roundness of the Earth, the rise and eclipse of the same sky lights at different times, and the appearance of this eclipse differently from each place, and how their appearance changes with distance.

In general, Al-Farghani's work "The book on the basics of astronomy" started the development of the science of astronomy in the countries of the Muslim East of the Middle Ages, and then in the countries of Europe through Spain. Ancient Greek science, including astronomy, first became known through treatises translated from Arabic. The Latin translation of Al-Farghani's work was published for the first time in 1493 by lithography. In 1669, the fame of Al-Farghani increased after the famous Dutch mathematician and Arabic scholar Jacob Golius published the Arabic text of Al-Farghani's work with a new Latin translation. In the 15th century, Regiomontane, a famous scientist of the European Renaissance, gave his lectures on astronomy at Austrian and Italian universities based on the

works of Al-Farghani. Al-Farghani's name is mentioned by Dante (14th century) and Schiller (18th century). European scientists D'alamber, Brokelman, H. Zuter, I. Yu. Krachkovskiy, A.P. Yushkevich, A. Rosenfeld highly appreciated AlFarghani's work and scientific legacy. 7 works of Al-Farghani have survived to our time (but these have not been translated into modern languages). The manuscripts of the works are stored in large libraries in different cities of the world - Berlin, Dushanbe, London, Paris, Tehran, Tashkent, Mashhad, Patna, Rampur, Aleppo and Cairo. A deep study of the rich scientific heritage of Ahmad al-Farghani began in Uzbekistan after independence. In 1998, the 1200th anniversary of AlFarghani was widely celebrated internationally. A park named after Al-Farghani and a statue of Al-Farghani were installed in the ancient city of Quwa. UNESCO's activities in 1998, according to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the celebration of the 1200th anniversary of the birth of Ahmad al-Farghani" (November 27, 1997) are dedicated to the life and work of the scholar. scientific conferences, art exhibitions were held, new books were published, plays (Piri Koinot by dramatist Hayitmat Rasul, "Child of Fergana" by Yoldosh Suleiman, "Bashar Alloma" by Nurullah Khan Haji Abdullah Ogle)) were staged, films were shot. One of the large 20 km craters on the moon is named after Ahmed al-Farghani. One of the squares, streets, and schools in Fergana city is named Al-Fargani. The name of Al-Farghani still remains in our respect and honor according to his services and legacies left to us. It is the duty of young people to master the knowledge and skills they have left behind, and preserve them by making good use of manuscripts. We should follow the path of knowledge of these scholars and seek the necessary knowledge for ourselves.

References:

1. Abdulahad Muhammadjanov, UzME. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000
2. Kari-Niyazov T.N, Astronomicheskaya school Ulugbeka, M.-L., 1950

3. Nosirov A., Hikmatullayev H., Ahmad Fargani, T., 1966.
4. Collection of materials of the scientific and practical conference of talented students of the republic April 12, 2023 "Al Farghani's scientific heritage, his contribution to the development of science, his place today." Tashkent in 2023.
5. <https://n.ziyouz.com> "Ahmad al-Farghani scientific world" Tashkent 2013